

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF EPIPHYTIC AND PATHOGENIC MICROBIOTA IN KUR-ARAZ PLAIN

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Abstract

At present, various determinants are used to determine the pathology caused by this or that fungus, most of which do not cover all the causative agents of the disease. At the same time, some data obtained in recent times indicate that species whose pathogenicity has not yet been confirmed can also cause pathologies. For this reason, it is very likely that the information about the registered pathogens is slightly lower than what is in the actual area.

Keywords: phytopathogenic, mycotoxins, agrophytocenosis, fungi, pathogenicity

The distribution of species involved in the formation of epiphytic and pathogenic mycobiota on plants shows that it is possible to distinguish it from any plants, as the fungi included in epiphytic mycobiota are almost all eurytrophs. As for the pathogens, the dependence in their distribution coincides with what was given in the first chapter of the work, that is, the species characterized by a rich mycobiota, at the same time, are the most populated places of fungi that cause various pathologies.

It should be noted that the danger of phytopathogenic fungi recorded in the Kura-Araz plain does not end only with the fact that they cause some pathology in this or that plant and cause a decrease in its biological activity. So, many of them use plants not only as a place of settlement for their activity, but also as a place of spillage of their metabolites. Such metabolites include mycotoxins, which can cause dangerous consequences not only for other living things, but also for human health. For example, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *A. niger*, *A. ochraceus*, *Fusarium culmorum*, *F. moniliforme*, *F. oxysporium*, *F. sporotrichioides*, etc. mushrooms are an example. Thus, they cause various pathologies in plants, as well as aflatoxin, ochratoxin A, fumonisin B-1 and B-2, zearalenone, etc. the synthesis of toxins, such as this, occurs as a result of the individual or joint participation of these fungi [5]. For example, as mentioned in the outbreak of fusarium disease, it occurs with the participation of species belonging to the genus *Fusarium*, and in this process, sometimes about 12 species of the mentioned genus are involved. In our research, it was determined that 8 species of this genus (*Fusarium avenaceum*, *F. culmorum*, *F. gibbosum*, *F. graminearum*, *F. moniliforme*, *F. oxysporium*, *F. solani* and *F. sporotrichioides*) are involved in the occurrence of this disease.

Material and method: All the species involved in the pathogenesis of the disease also secrete mycotoxins,

including fumonisin B-1 and B-2, T-2, NT-2, neocolanin, diacetoxycystyrpenol, fusarin-S, stergmatocystin, aurofusarin, zearalenone. etc. can be shown [5,3,4]. Another example. Fungi belonging to the genera *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* are involved in the pathogenesis of mold disease in plants, and at the same time toxins are synthesized as a result of the joint activity of fungal species belonging to these two genera. Ochratoxin is the product of such an "activity" that species such as *A. ochraceus* and *P. verucosum* participate in its formation [200].

The fact that the mentioned mycotoxins are dangerous for human health can be considered as one of the facts that have been confirmed today. So, as a result of the conducted studies, the number of mycotoxins isolated from mushrooms is up to 2000. Of these, 47 were found to have high toxicity, and 15 to have carcinogenic and mutagenic effects. Among those with carcinogenic effects are aflatoxins, ochratoxin A, zearalenone, T-2, fuzarenone X, etc. toxins are also included [4,2,6]. In addition, fumanosin B-1 has been found to have a negative effect on all aspects of the immune system [1,9].

Fungi belonging to the genus *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. ochraceus*, *P. cuculopium*, *Alternaria alternata*, etc., involved in the synthesis of the mentioned mycotoxins. and fungi like are among the species that actively participate in the formation of the mycobiota of cultivated plants in the Kura-Araz plain where the research is conducted. In addition to what has been said, many plant products, such as fruits, vegetables and melons, are used by people without special thermal treatment, and today the normative documents regulating the number of fungi that synthesize toxic metabolites in these types of products are not perfect. , or not at all, then the consideration of these issues should be accepted as an unquestionable reality.

It is known that they are used in various vegetative and generative organs of cultivated plants for food purposes, and for this reason, the distribution of fungi on separate organs of plants is of certain scientific and practical interest. For this reason, in the course of research, observations were made that allowed to clarify this issue. As a result, it became clear that the distribution of the fungi causing the pathology on the vegetative and generative organs of the host plant is also different, and some of the pathogens are universal

and some are specific. The characterization of the recorded phytopathogenic fungi in this aspect showed that the most frequent place of disease is the stem and leaves of plants, followed by flowers and fruits, which are generative organs, and the last place is taken by the roots of plants, the quantitative expression of which is reflected in table 1. As it can be seen, a total of 23.2% of registered pathologies are universal in nature, while the remaining 76.8% are specific to one degree or another.

Table 1

Characterization of phytopathogenic fungi according to their presence on the vegetative and generative organs of the studied plants

The name of the organ causing the pathology	The number of registered pathologies	Share in the total recorded pathology (%)
Pathologies recorded in the trunk	42	60.9
Pathologies recorded on the leaf	39	56.5
Pathologies recorded in the root	10	14.5
Pathologies recorded in fruits and flowers	28	40.6
Pathologies recorded only in vegetative organs	41	59.4
Pathologies recorded only in generative organs	12	17,4
Pathologies recorded in both vegetative and generative organs	16	23,2

As a conclusion of the research conducted in connection with the study of the mycobiota of cultivated plants in the Kura-Araz plain, it was considered appropriate to evaluate the phytosanitary condition of individual agrocenoses in that area according to fungal pathologies.

It should be noted that today there is no universal, i.e. universally accepted, approach to the evaluation of agrophytocenoses. True, in this regard, there are international agreements to which countries, including the Republic of Azerbaijan, have joined, and those agreements are basically framework documents. However, due to the lack of perfect normative

documents arising from that document and taking into account local specifics, even today certain problems in evaluating this or that agrophytocenosis according to the degree of danger of pathologies remain unsolved. For this reason, during the assessment of agrophytocenoses where cultivated plants are grown in the Kura-Araz plain, it was considered appropriate to use a 5-point evaluation scale, which was summarized based on literature data and normative documents adopted in the Russian Federation [1,7,8] and was compiled mainly according to the degree of prevalence of pathology (pp. 2).

Table 2

Characteristics of the assessment of the phytosanitary status of agrocenoses where vegetables and melons are cultivated by points

The state of agrophytocenoses according to the prevalence of pathology	Systematization of registered pathologies according to the degree of prevalence
up to 10%	Rot (except gray rot), septoria (cereals), downy mildew, cercosporiosis, anthracnose, powdery mildew, sclerotinosis, cladosporiosis, alternariosis, false powdery mildew, fusarium (cereals), verticilliosis (tomato), rust, rust, phytophthora
(Normal)	Spotting (except ascochytioid), fusarium (beans), gray rot, septoria (tomato), verticilliosis (cotton)
10-20%	Ascochytioid spot (bean and pea)

From the obtained results, it became clear that today the state of agrophytocenoses where cultivated plants are cultivated in the Kura-Araz plain is generally either normal or sufficient, and in these cases, it is recorded that the prevalence of pathology is not higher than 20%, which is recorded only in ascochytioid spotting. that is, a potentially dangerous situation is observed due to this disease. Direct research allows us to note that the phytosanitary condition of the agrophytocenoses used for the cultivation of cultivated plants in the Kura-Araz plain is not so dangerous. However, it is unlikely that this situation will remain

stable forever. Thus, during the research period, it was observed that the prevalence rate of a number of pathological agents recorded in this way increased.

Therefore, the monitoring system of diseases should be constantly improved, the preparation of preventive measures against pathogens, the use of durable and productive varieties for planting should be among the important tasks of both practitioners and theorists.

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